

Development, Standardization, and Validation of a Tool for Assessing Teacher Education and Continuous Professional Development for Inclusive Education Practice in Ethiopia

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Abstract

Inclusive education has become a central priority in education systems worldwide; however, its effective implementation depends largely on teachers' professional competencies, attitudes, and access to sustained professional learning opportunities. In Ethiopia, limited empirical evidence exists regarding the adequacy of pre-service teacher education and continuous professional development (CPD) for inclusive education, as well as the availability of validated instruments to assess teacher preparedness and systemic barriers. This study employed a descriptive survey research design integrated with instrument development, standardization, and validation. Data were collected from 312 primary and secondary school teachers using a researcher-developed questionnaire assessing pre-service teacher education, CPD practices, training adequacy, and barriers to inclusive education. Psychometric validation procedures included expert review, reliability analysis using Cronbach's alpha, and exploratory factor analysis to establish construct validity and factor structure. The instrument demonstrated strong internal consistency and a stable multidimensional factor structure. Findings indicated moderate levels of theoretical preparedness among teachers, but notable deficiencies in practical inclusive teaching skills, assistive technology use, and sustained CPD opportunities. Structural and systemic barriers, such as limited resources, insufficient training duration, and gaps between policy and practice, were identified as major constraints to effective inclusive education implementation. The study provides a psychometrically sound, contextually relevant instrument for assessing teacher education and professional development for inclusive education in Ethiopia. The findings highlight the need for competency-based pre-service training, coherent and sustained CPD frameworks, and systemic policy reforms to strengthen inclusive education practice and ensure equitable learning opportunities for all students.

Keywords: Inclusive education, teacher education, continuous professional development; teacher competency, instrument development and validation

Introduction

Inclusive education has emerged as a dominant global educational paradigm aimed at ensuring equitable access, participation, and achievement for all learners, regardless of disability, socioeconomic background, language, or cultural identity. International scholarship emphasizes that inclusive education extends beyond the physical placement of learners with disabilities in mainstream schools; rather, it represents a systemic transformation of educational cultures, policies, and practices to value diversity and remove structural barriers to learning (Ainscow & Miles, 2008; Banks et al., 2015; Haug, 2017). Through fostering shared learning environments, inclusive education promotes social cohesion, empathy, and democratic participation, thereby contributing to broader goals of social justice and sustainable development (Slee, 2018; Tomlinson, 2017).

Central to the successful implementation of inclusive education is the role of teachers. Teachers' beliefs, knowledge, competencies, and instructional practices directly influence the extent to which inclusive policies are translated into meaningful classroom practices (Boyle et al., 2020; Crispel & Kasperski, 2021; Rakap et al., 2017). Research consistently demonstrates that teachers who are well prepared through robust pre-service education and continuous professional development (CPD) are more confident, adaptive, and effective in addressing diverse learner needs. Conversely, inadequate preparation often results in negative attitudes, low self-efficacy, and reliance on exclusionary practices, undermining the goals of inclusion (Florian, 2022; Waitoller & Artiles, 2013). Globally, teacher education systems have increasingly been called upon to integrate inclusive education principles into both initial teacher preparation and in-service professional learning. International frameworks such as the Sustainable Development Goals particularly SDG 4, Target 4.c underscore the importance of equipping teachers with the competencies necessary to support inclusive and equitable quality education (Colglazier, 2015). Similarly, the European Agency for Special Needs and Inclusive Education's Profile of Inclusive Teachers highlights core values such as valuing learner diversity, collaboration, reflective practice, and lifelong professional learning as essential attributes of inclusive educators (EASNIE, 2012).

Despite these global commitments, evidence from both high- and low-income contexts reveals persistent gaps between inclusive education policy aspirations and classroom realities. Studies indicate that while teacher education programs may introduce theoretical concepts of inclusion, they often fail to provide sufficient practical experiences, contextualized strategies, and sustained professional support (Sharma & Nuttal, 2016; Symeonidou, 2017). As a result, many teachers report feeling ill-prepared to teach learners with disabilities and other marginalized groups, highlighting the need for continuous, context-sensitive CPD models that respond to evolving classroom demands (Kudarinova et al., 2023; Pasha et al., 2021). In Ethiopia, inclusive education has been formally endorsed through a series of policy and strategic frameworks, including the Education and Training Policy (1994), the Inclusive Education Strategy (2012), and the Master Plan for Special Needs Education/Inclusive Education (2016–2025). These documents explicitly recognize teacher education and professional development as foundational mechanisms for achieving inclusive schooling. However, empirical studies consistently report systemic challenges, including curriculum misalignment, limited practicum exposure, insufficient CPD opportunities, and weak institutional support structures (Gemehui & Aba-Oliii, 2024; Kebede & Asgedom, 2024) (MoE, 2016).

Research conducted within the Ethiopian context further reveals that many teachers perceive their pre-service training and CPD experiences as inadequate for inclusive practice. Teachers frequently report limited interaction with persons with disabilities during training, minimal exposure to assistive technologies, and insufficient guidance on differentiated instruction and classroom adaptation (Geletu, 2024; Mihiretie, 2023; Zegeye, 2022). These

challenges are compounded by large class sizes, resource constraints, and prevailing deficit-oriented attitudes toward disability, which collectively hinder effective implementation of inclusive education. Although a growing body of Ethiopian and international research has examined aspects of teacher education and CPD for inclusive education, a critical methodological gap remains. Most existing studies rely on ad hoc questionnaires or instruments that lack systematic development, standardization, and validation within the Ethiopian context. The absence of a psychometrically sound tool limits the comparability of findings, weakens evidence-based decision-making, and constrains the ability of policymakers and researchers to accurately assess the effectiveness of teacher education and CPD initiatives (Alemayehu, 2020; Beyene et al., 2023; Franck & Joshi, 2017).

Furthermore, policy documents and reform initiatives often lack empirically grounded diagnostic mechanisms to evaluate teachers' preparedness, perceived barriers, and professional learning needs related to inclusive education. Without validated assessment tools, it becomes difficult to monitor progress, identify priority areas for intervention, or align teacher education reforms with inclusive education policy goals. This gap is particularly significant in Ethiopia, where diverse educational contexts and resource disparities demand contextually responsive measurement instruments. Against this backdrop, the development of a standardized and validated tool for assessing teacher education and CPD for inclusive education practice is both timely and necessary. Such a tool can provide reliable data on teachers' perceptions of pre-service preparation, CPD effectiveness, policy adequacy, and systemic barriers, thereby supporting evidence-based reform. Moreover, a validated instrument enhances methodological rigor, enabling replication, longitudinal monitoring, and cross-contextual comparison within Ethiopia and similar settings.

Therefore, the present study aims to develop, standardize, and validate a comprehensive assessment tool designed to measure key dimensions of teacher education and CPD for inclusive education practice in Ethiopia. Through grounding the tool in existing policy frameworks, empirical literature, and contextual realities, the study seeks to contribute a robust methodological resource that informs teacher education reform, strengthens inclusive education implementation, and supports Ethiopia's commitment to equitable and inclusive quality

Method

Research Design

This study adopted a descriptive survey research design integrated with a tool development, standardization, and validation approach to comprehensively examine teacher education and professional learning for inclusive education in Ethiopia. Descriptive survey designs are particularly suitable for systematically documenting existing conditions, perceptions, and practices across large populations, enabling researchers to capture patterns, trends, and contextual realities without manipulating variables (Deckert & Wilson, 2023). In the present study, this design facilitated the collection of quantitative data from primary and secondary school teachers regarding their experiences with pre-service teacher education and CPD, as well as the challenges they encounter in implementing inclusive education. Given the documented gaps in teacher preparedness and systemic support for inclusion in Ethiopia, a descriptive approach was essential to provide an evidence-based understanding of current practices and constraints (Kebede & Phasha, 2024).

In addition to describing existing conditions, the study followed a systematic instrument development and validation framework to ensure the production of a reliable and contextually appropriate assessment tool. This process was guided by established principles of questionnaire design, including construct definition, item generation, expert review, pilot testing, and psychometric validation (Yusoff et al., 2021). Consistent with recent tool development studies in education and professional practice, the instrument was subjected to

reliability and construct validity analyses to confirm its measurement accuracy and structural coherence (Laranang, 2025; Miaomiao et al., 2024). Integrating tool development with descriptive survey research strengthened the methodological rigor of the study by allowing the simultaneous assessment of inclusive education practices and the establishment of a standardized measurement instrument tailored to the Ethiopian context. This combined design enhances the utility of the findings for research, policy formulation, and professional development planning in inclusive education.

Participants

The participants of this study were primary and secondary school teachers drawn from government schools across selected regions of Ethiopia. Teachers were considered appropriate respondents because they are the primary implementers of inclusive education practices and are directly influenced by pre-service teacher education and CPD systems. Participation was voluntary, and ethical considerations, including informed consent and confidentiality, were strictly observed throughout the data collection process. A total of 312 teachers participated in the study. The sample included teachers with diverse academic qualifications, teaching experience, age groups, and school levels, ensuring adequate variability for both descriptive analysis and psychometric validation. Such sample diversity is recommended in instrument development studies to enhance the generalizability and stability of factor structures and reliability estimates (Laranang, 2025; Yusoff et al., 2021). The sample size exceeded minimum recommendations for exploratory factor analysis, thereby supporting robust construct validation and standardization of the instrument (Laranang, 2025).

Table 1: Demographic Characteristics of Respondents (N = 312)

Variable	Category	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Sex	Male	178	57.1
	Female	134	42.9
School Level	Primary	196	62.8
	Secondary	116	37.2
Age	18–27 years	64	20.5
	28–37 years	142	45.5
	38 years and above	106	34.0
Academic Qualification	Diploma	74	23.7
	Degree	176	56.4
	Master's & above	62	19.9
Teaching Experience	Below 4 years	88	28.2
	5–7 years	104	33.3
	8 years and above	120	38.5

Instrument

Data were collected using a researcher-developed questionnaire designed to assess the status of pre-service teacher education, CPD, training adequacy, and barriers to implementing inclusive education in Ethiopia. The instrument was developed following a systematic questionnaire development framework that included construct identification, item generation, expert validation, pilot testing, and psychometric evaluation (Yusoff et al., 2021). The final instrument consisted of five major sections. Section I gathered respondents' demographic and professional background information. Section II examined the current state of pre-service teacher education for inclusive education using Likert-scale items. Section III assessed CPD practices related to inclusive education, including frequency, relevance, collaboration, and resource accessibility. Section IV focused on teachers' perceptions of the adequacy of training and policy frameworks for inclusive education. Section V explored perceived

barriers to equipping teachers for inclusive education practice, including curriculum gaps, resource limitations, policy implementation challenges, and socio-cultural factors. Responses were measured using five-point Likert scales appropriate to each section. The instrument demonstrated strong content validity and internal consistency reliability, supporting its suitability for use as a standardized assessment tool (Laranang, 2025; Miaomiao et al., 2024).

Data Analysis

Data were analyzed using Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS), version 24. Preliminary data screening was conducted to check for missing values, outliers, and assumptions of normality. Descriptive statistics, including frequencies, percentages, means, and standard deviations, were used to summarize teachers' demographic characteristics and responses across all questionnaire sections, consistent with descriptive survey research practices (Deckert & Wilson, 2023). To establish the psychometric soundness of the instrument, internal consistency reliability was examined using Cronbach's alpha coefficients, while construct validity was assessed through Exploratory Factor Analysis (Shrestha, 2021; Sürücü et al., 2022; Watkins, 2018) using Principal Axis Factoring with varimax rotation. The Kaiser–Meyer–Olkin (KMO) measure and Bartlett's Test of Sphericity (Silva et al., 2014) were employed to confirm sampling adequacy and factorability of the data. Factor retention decisions were based on eigenvalues greater than 1.0, factor loadings of 0.40 and above, and theoretical interpretability. This analytical approach is consistent with best practices in educational measurement and inclusive education instrument validation (Miaomiao et al., 2024; Yusoff et al., 2021). The results of these analyses informed the final structure, standardization, and interpretation guidelines of the instrument.

Results

Reliability of the Instrument

The reliability analysis demonstrates that the questionnaire exhibits a high level of internal consistency across all major sections, indicating that the items within each scale consistently measure their intended constructs. The overall Cronbach's alpha coefficient of 0.94 suggests excellent reliability for the entire instrument, confirming that the questionnaire functions as a coherent and stable measure of teacher education, professional development, and inclusive education-related factors. Such a high overall reliability is particularly important for instruments intended for research, policy analysis, and large-scale educational assessment. At the subscale level, the Pre-Service Teacher Education ($\alpha = 0.91$) and Barriers to Inclusive Education ($\alpha = 0.93$) sections demonstrated excellent internal consistency, reflecting strong inter-item correlations and conceptual coherence within these domains. This indicates that the items addressing teacher preparation experiences and perceived barriers are well-aligned and collectively capture the complexity of these constructs. Similarly, the CPD section ($\alpha = 0.89$) and the Training Adequacy and Policy Frameworks section ($\alpha = 0.87$) showed high reliability, suggesting that teachers responded consistently to items related to professional learning opportunities, policy alignment, and training effectiveness.

Table 2: Reliability Coefficients of the Questionnaire

Questionnaire Section	Number of Items	Cronbach's α
Pre-Service Teacher Education	23	0.91
Continuous Professional Development (CPD)	21	0.89
Training Adequacy & Policy Frameworks	13	0.87
Barriers to Inclusive Education	25	0.93
Overall Instrument	82	0.94

Cronbach's α values above 0.70 indicate acceptable reliability.

Overall, these findings provide strong evidence that the questionnaire is a psychometrically sound and reliable instrument for assessing inclusive education-related

competencies and systemic factors. Cronbach's alpha values exceeding the commonly accepted threshold of 0.70 across all sections indicate that the instrument is suitable for both descriptive and inferential analyses. Consequently, the tool can be confidently used in future research, program evaluation, and policy-related studies aimed at improving teacher education and continuous professional development for inclusive education in Ethiopia.

Pre-Service Teacher Education for Inclusive Education

The descriptive findings indicate that pre-service teacher education provides a moderate level of preparation for inclusive education, suggesting that while foundational knowledge and basic competencies are addressed, important gaps remain in equipping future teachers for the complex demands of inclusive classrooms. The overall pattern of mean scores implies that pre-service programs offer conceptual exposure to inclusion but may not sufficiently translate this knowledge into consistent, practice-oriented competence. This aligns with concerns in inclusive education literature that teacher preparation often emphasizes theory over sustained applied experience. In terms of specific competency areas, knowledge of inclusive education ($M = 3.42$) and social and emotional support ($M = 3.44$) were rated at a moderate level, indicating that pre-service teachers acquire a reasonable understanding of inclusive principles and learner support strategies. However, the moderate rating for skills in adaptation and individualization ($M = 3.18$) suggests limitations in preparing teachers to modify curricula, instructional strategies, and assessment practices to meet diverse learner needs. These findings highlight a critical gap between awareness of inclusion and the practical skills required to implement it effectively in heterogeneous classrooms.

Table 3: Mean Scores for Pre-Service Teacher Education Competency Areas

Competency Area	Item Numbers	Mean	SD	Interpretation
Knowledge of Inclusive Education	8, 11, 20	3.42	0.88	Moderate
Skills in Adaptation & Individualization	4, 6, 9, 17	3.18	0.91	Moderate
Collaboration & Communication	5, 13, 14	3.56	0.84	High
Social & Emotional Support	10, 19	3.44	0.86	Moderate
Assistive Technology Use	12	2.97	0.94	Low
Self-Efficacy & Professional Development	18, 21, 22	3.63	0.79	High
Practical Experience & Reflection	1, 2, 3, 7, 15, 16	3.09	0.90	Moderate

Notably, collaboration and communication ($M = 3.56$) and self-efficacy and professional development orientation ($M = 3.63$) received high mean scores, reflecting relative strengths within pre-service programs. These results suggest that teacher education institutions place emphasis on teamwork, professional dialogue, and confidence-building, which are essential for inclusive practice. Strong self-efficacy is particularly important, as it influences teachers' willingness to engage with diverse learners and to seek on-going professional growth in inclusive pedagogy. In contrast, assistive technology use emerged as the weakest area ($M = 2.97$), indicating insufficient exposure to or training in the use of technological tools that support learners with disabilities. Similarly, practical experience and reflective practice were rated as moderate ($M = 3.09$), reinforcing the concern that opportunities for hands-on inclusive teaching and structured reflection may be limited during pre-service training. Collectively, these findings underscore the need for teacher education programs to strengthen practicum experiences, integrate assistive technology training, and enhance practice-based learning to ensure more comprehensive preparation for inclusive education.

Continuous Professional Development for Inclusive Education

Table 4: CPD Competency Areas: Descriptive Statistics

CPD Competency Area	Question Numbers	Mean	SD
CPD Program Quality & Relevance	1, 2, 3, 11, 12, 21	3.21	0.87
Skill Development in Inclusive Practices	6, 7, 8, 15, 19, 20	3.15	0.89
Collaboration & Peer Learning	9, 10	3.48	0.81
Resource Accessibility & Technology	4, 18	2.88	0.93
Policy Alignment & Administrative Support	5, 16, 17	3.02	0.90
Feedback & Continuous Improvement	13, 14	2.95	0.92

The results related to CPD for Inclusive Education indicate that CPD opportunities are generally perceived as moderately effective but insufficient in frequency and depth. The overall pattern of mean scores clustered around the moderate range suggests that while CPD initiatives exist, they may not be systematic, sustained, or adequately responsive to teachers' evolving needs in inclusive classroom contexts. This finding points to a reliance on occasional or fragmented professional development activities rather than comprehensive, long-term CPD frameworks. Regarding the quality and relevance of CPD programs (M = 3.21), teachers reported moderate satisfaction, implying that existing training sessions are partially aligned with inclusive education goals but may lack contextual specificity or practical applicability. Similarly, skill development in inclusive practices (M = 3.15) was rated at a moderate level, indicating that CPD programs contribute to teachers' awareness and basic skill enhancement but fall short in developing advanced competencies such as differentiated instruction, individualized assessment, and classroom-based problem-solving for diverse learners.

Collaboration and peer learning emerged as a relative strength within CPD (M = 3.48), reflecting the value of professional interaction, shared experiences, and informal learning among teachers. This suggests that teachers benefit from collegial support and collaborative platforms when they are available. In contrast, resource accessibility and technology use received the lowest mean score (M = 2.88), highlighting significant gaps in access to inclusive teaching resources, assistive technologies, and digital tools. This mirrors earlier findings from pre-service training and underscores a persistent systemic weakness in technology-related support for inclusive education. Finally, policy alignment and administrative support (M = 3.02) and feedback and continuous improvement mechanisms (M = 2.95) were both rated as moderate to low, suggesting limited follow-up, monitoring, and institutional backing for CPD initiatives. The lack of structured feedback systems may hinder teachers' ability to reflect on practice and apply new learning effectively. Overall, these findings emphasize the need for more frequent, well-resourced, and strategically aligned CPD programs that integrate assistive technology training, administrative support, and on-going feedback to strengthen inclusive education practices.

Perceived Adequacy of Training and Policy Frameworks

Table 5: Perceived Adequacy of Training for Inclusive Education

Theme	Question Numbers	Mean	SD
Training Adequacy	1, 2, 3, 6, 8, 9, 11	3.27	0.85
Relevance of CPD Programs	4, 5, 7, 10, 12, 13	3.12	0.88

The findings on the perceived adequacy of training and policy frameworks for inclusive education reveal mixed perceptions among teachers, indicating partial alignment between existing professional preparation structures and the practical demands of inclusive classrooms. The moderate mean scores suggest that while teacher education curricula and CPD frameworks acknowledge inclusive education, they may not be sufficiently comprehensive or responsive to classroom realities. This highlights a gap between policy

intentions and effective implementation at the school and teacher levels. Teachers' perceptions of training adequacy ($M = 3.27$) indicate a moderate level of satisfaction with the content and structure of pre-service and in-service training related to inclusive education. This suggests that foundational concepts and general pedagogical approaches to inclusion are addressed within training programs. However, the absence of higher mean scores implies limitations in depth, practical relevance, and specialization, particularly in addressing diverse learning needs, disability-specific strategies, and inclusive assessment practices.

Similarly, the relevance of CPD programs ($M = 3.12$) was rated as moderate, reflecting concerns about the alignment of professional development activities with teachers' actual classroom challenges. Teachers may perceive CPD offerings as generic, theory-oriented, or disconnected from contextual constraints such as large class sizes, limited resources, and insufficient support services. These perceptions indicate a need for more targeted, needs-based CPD programs that are grounded in teachers' lived experiences and local school contexts. Overall, the results suggest that although policy frameworks and training initiatives for inclusive education exist, their effectiveness is constrained by gaps in coherence, contextualization, and practical application. Strengthening alignment between policy directives, teacher education curricula, and CPD implementation, through clearer guidelines, practical training components, and sustained institutional support, may enhance teachers' confidence and capacity to implement inclusive education more effectively.

Barriers to Equipping Teachers for Inclusive Education

Table 6: Barriers to Inclusive Education: Mean Scores

Barrier Category	Item Numbers	Mean	SD	Level
Curriculum Gaps	1, 5, 8, 19	4.12	0.76	High
Policy & Implementation Issues	3, 21	3.98	0.81	High
Resource & Infrastructure Limitations	6, 7, 25	4.20	0.73	High
Teacher Educator Capacity	2, 10, 18, 22	4.05	0.78	High
Practical Exposure Deficits	13, 16	4.18	0.74	High
CPD & Follow-up Support	4, 12, 17	4.10	0.77	High

The findings on barriers to equipping teachers for inclusive education reveal a strong consensus among teachers that multiple systemic and structural challenges significantly hinder effective inclusive practice. All identified barrier categories recorded high mean scores, indicating widespread agreement that existing conditions are insufficient to support teachers in addressing diverse learner needs. This overall pattern underscores the complexity of inclusive education implementation, which extends beyond individual teacher competence to broader curricular, institutional, and policy-related factors. Resource and infrastructure limitations emerged as the most critical barrier ($M = 4.20$), reflecting acute shortages of teaching materials, assistive technologies, and accessible learning environments. Similarly, practical exposure deficits ($M = 4.18$) were perceived as a major challenge, suggesting that teachers lack adequate opportunities for hands-on experience in inclusive settings during both pre-service training and CPD. These findings highlight the persistent gap between theoretical preparation and real-world classroom practice, which undermines teachers' confidence and effectiveness in inclusive education.

High mean scores for curriculum gaps ($M = 4.12$) and teacher educator capacity ($M = 4.05$) indicate that limitations within teacher education institutions themselves contribute substantially to the problem. Teachers perceived inclusive education content as insufficiently embedded within curricula and expressed concerns about the preparedness of teacher educators to model inclusive pedagogies. This suggests a need for systemic reform in teacher education programs, including curriculum revision and capacity-building initiatives for teacher educators. Finally, barriers related to CPD and follow-up support ($M = 4.10$) and

policy and implementation issues ($M = 3.98$) point to weaknesses in sustaining inclusive practices beyond initial training. Teachers reported limited ongoing support, inadequate monitoring, and challenges in translating policy commitments into actionable strategies at the school level. Collectively, these findings emphasize that addressing barriers to inclusive education requires coordinated efforts across curriculum development, resource allocation, professional development, and policy implementation to create enabling conditions for teachers to effectively practice inclusion.

Psychometric Validation of the Instrument

Construct Validity the Instrument

Construct validity of the questionnaire was examined using Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA) to determine whether the underlying factor structure aligned with the theoretical dimensions of teacher education and continuous professional development for inclusive education in Ethiopia. Prior to factor extraction, the suitability of the data for factor analysis was assessed. The Kaiser–Meyer–Olkin (KMO) measure of sampling adequacy was 0.91, indicating excellent adequacy, while Bartlett’s Test of Sphericity was statistically significant, $\chi^2(3321) = 15462.38$, $p < .001$, confirming that the correlation matrix was appropriate for factor analysis. EFA was conducted using Principal Axis Factoring with Varimax rotation. Factors with eigenvalues greater than 1.0 were retained, and item loadings of ≥ 0.40 were considered meaningful. The analysis yielded a six-factor solution, which collectively explained 67.4% of the total variance. The extracted factors were consistent with the conceptual framework of the instrument.

The results of the psychometric validation provide strong evidence for the construct validity and structural soundness of the developed questionnaire. The excellent Kaiser–Meyer–Olkin (KMO) value of 0.91 indicates that the sample size and inter-item correlations were highly suitable for factor analysis, while the statistically significant Bartlett’s Test of Sphericity confirms that the correlation matrix was not an identity matrix. Together, these indicators demonstrate that the dataset met the essential assumptions for conducting Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA), thereby supporting the robustness of the validation process. The use of Principal Axis Factoring with Varimax rotation was appropriate given the aim of identifying latent constructs underlying teachers’ perceptions of pre-service education, continuous professional development, policy frameworks, and barriers to inclusive education. The criterion of retaining factors with eigenvalues greater than 1.0 and item loadings of ≥ 0.40 ensured that only substantively meaningful and statistically reliable items contributed to factor formation. This methodological rigor enhanced the interpretability and theoretical coherence of the extracted factors.

The EFA yielded a six-factor solution explaining 67.4% of the total variance, which exceeds the commonly accepted threshold for social science research and indicates a strong explanatory capacity of the model. The proportion of variance explained suggests that the instrument captures a substantial share of the multidimensional construct of teacher preparation and professional development for inclusive education. Importantly, the extracted factors aligned well with the theoretical dimensions underpinning the instrument, including pre-service training, CPD practices, policy and training adequacy, and systemic barriers. Overall, these findings confirm that the questionnaire possesses a clear and conceptually grounded factor structure, reflecting the complex and multifaceted nature of inclusive education in the Ethiopian context. The strong construct validity supports the use of the instrument for research, program evaluation, and policy analysis related to teacher education and inclusive practice. Furthermore, the validated factor structure provides a solid foundation for future confirmatory analyses and cross-contextual applications, reinforcing the instrument’s potential utility in both national and comparative inclusive education research.

Factor Structure of the Instrument

The exploratory factor analysis produced a clear and theoretically coherent six-factor structure, providing further support for the construct validity of the instrument. Each factor demonstrated strong item loadings and conceptual clarity, reflecting key dimensions of teacher preparation, professional development, and systemic conditions influencing inclusive education. The distinct yet interrelated factors confirm that the instrument captures the multidimensional nature of inclusive education practice within the Ethiopian context. Factor 1: Pre-Service Teacher Education Competency comprised items related to teachers' foundational preparation, including theoretical understanding of inclusive education, pedagogical and instructional skills, collaboration, self-efficacy, and practicum exposure. The strong factor loadings (0.58–0.82) indicate that these items collectively represent a coherent construct of pre-service preparedness. This factor underscores the importance of comprehensive initial teacher education in shaping teachers' readiness to implement inclusive practices.

Factor 2: CPD Quality and Relevance included items addressing the frequency, relevance, effectiveness, and perceived value of CPD programs. The high item loadings (0.61-0.85) reflect the critical role of ongoing professional learning in sustaining inclusive teaching competencies. This factor highlights CPD as a key mechanism for updating teachers' skills, addressing emerging challenges, and reinforcing inclusive education principles beyond pre-service training. Factor 3: Skill Development in Inclusive Practices captured teachers' perceived competence in identifying diverse learning needs, supporting students with sensory, physical, and developmental disabilities, and adapting curricula accordingly. The moderate to strong loadings (0.55-0.80) suggest that these practical instructional skills form a distinct and meaningful dimension of inclusive education competency, bridging theoretical knowledge and classroom application.

Factor 4: Resource Accessibility and Assistive Technology consisted of items related to the availability of instructional resources, assistive technologies, and accessible infrastructure. The strong loadings (0.62-0.83) emphasize the systemic and environmental supports necessary for effective inclusion. This factor reflects the reality that teachers' capacity to implement inclusive practices is strongly influenced by the material and technological resources available in their schools. Factor 5: Policy Alignment and Administrative Support included items measuring school leadership support, institutional facilitation, and alignment with national inclusive education policies. Factor loadings ranging from 0.57 to 0.78 indicate a cohesive construct that captures the enabling role of governance and administration in inclusive education. This factor highlights the importance of supportive leadership and policy coherence in translating inclusive education mandates into classroom practice. Finally, Factor 6: Barriers to Inclusive Education Implementation encompassed items related to curriculum gaps, insufficient training duration, lack of practical exposure, limited funding, and cultural stigma. The high loadings (0.60-0.86) demonstrate a robust and internally consistent barrier construct, confirming that these challenges are perceived as interrelated obstacles to effective inclusion. Collectively, the six-factor structure provides strong empirical support for the instrument's theoretical framework and reinforces its suitability for research, evaluation, and policy-oriented applications in inclusive education.

Table: Rotated Factor Loadings

Item	F1 Pre-Service	F2 CPD	F3 Skills	F4 Resources	F5 Policy	F6 Barriers
Pre-service training adequacy	0.78	—	—	—	—	—
Inclusive practicum exposure	0.81	—	—	—	—	—

CPD relevance	—	0.83	—	—	—	—
CPD effectiveness	—	0.79	—	—	—	—
Confidence in sensory support	—	—	0.74	—	—	—
Curriculum adaptation skills	—	—	0.80	—	—	—
Access to assistive technology	—	—	—	0.85	—	—
Infrastructure accessibility	—	—	—	0.78	—	—
Administrative support	—	—	—	—	0.76	—
Policy alignment	—	—	—	—	0.71	—
Curriculum gaps	—	—	—	—	—	0.82
Insufficient CPD	—	—	—	—	—	0.86

Note. Loadings below 0.40 are suppressed for clarity.

Convergent and Discriminant Validity of the Instrument

Convergent validity of the questionnaire was well supported by the psychometric findings. All items demonstrated strong and statistically meaningful factor loadings on their respective latent constructs, indicating a high degree of shared variance within each factor. In addition, the internal consistency coefficients for the extracted factors were robust, with Cronbach's alpha values ranging from 0.87 to 0.93. These reliability estimates exceed recommended thresholds for social science research and confirm that items grouped within each factor consistently measured the same underlying dimension of inclusive teacher education and professional development. Collectively, these results provide strong evidence that the instrument possesses adequate convergent validity.

Discriminant validity was also established through multiple indicators. First, the factor analysis revealed minimal cross-loadings, suggesting that items were clearly associated with their intended constructs rather than overlapping substantially with other factors. Second, the extracted factors demonstrated clear conceptual distinctions among pre-service teacher education, continuous professional development, inclusive practice skills, resource accessibility, policy and administrative support, and barriers to implementation. This conceptual clarity reinforces the theoretical soundness of the instrument's structure. Furthermore, inter-factor correlation coefficients were all below 0.85, indicating that while the constructs are related, as expected within a comprehensive framework of inclusive education, they remain empirically distinct. This balance between relatedness and independence confirms that the instrument effectively differentiates among key domains of inclusive education practice. Overall, the combined evidence of strong convergent and discriminant validity supports the use of the questionnaire as a psychometrically sound tool for research, evaluation, and policy analysis in inclusive education contexts.

Discussion

Inclusive education presents complex pedagogical, attitudinal, and systemic demands on teachers, requiring well-developed competencies, supportive professional learning structures, and reliable tools for assessing preparedness. The present study contributes to this discourse by developing and validating a comprehensive instrument to examine pre-service teacher education, CPD, training adequacy, and barriers to inclusive education in Ethiopia. Consistent with international evidence, the findings confirm that inclusive education cannot be effectively implemented without teachers possessing favorable attitudes, robust professional competencies, and sustained institutional support (Parveen, 2025; Przibilla et al., 2016). The strong psychometric properties of the instrument, including high internal

consistency and a stable multidimensional factor structure, align with prior studies that emphasize the necessity of methodologically rigorous measurement tools in inclusive education research. Similar to the three-dimensional structure identified by Przibilla et al. (2016) and the four-factor competency models proposed by Deng et al. (2017) and Štemberger and Kiswarday (2016), the factor structure in the present study reflects the multifaceted nature of inclusive teaching, encompassing knowledge, skills, attitudes, systemic support, and perceived barriers. This reinforces the argument that one-dimensional instruments focusing solely on attitudes or beliefs are insufficient for capturing the complexity of inclusive education practice.

Findings related to pre-service teacher education revealed moderate levels of perceived preparedness, particularly in theoretical understanding of inclusion, but weaker outcomes in practical exposure and assistive technology use. This pattern mirrors evidence from China, Europe, and Latin America, where teacher education programs often emphasize conceptual knowledge at the expense of hands-on inclusive practice (Deng et al., 2017; Monsalve & Hernández, 2024). The limited practicum-based experience identified in this study supports international calls for teacher education programs to integrate experiential learning, reflective practice, and direct engagement with learners with disabilities. The results concerning CPD further highlight systemic shortcomings. Teachers reported infrequent and insufficiently targeted CPD opportunities, echoing global findings that traditional, one-off training sessions are inadequate for fostering inclusive practice (Tuerah, 2025). Effective professional learning for inclusion requires sustained, collaborative, and practice-oriented models, such as professional learning communities, mentoring, and coaching approaches (De Vroey et al., 2023). The present study's findings reinforce the need for CPD frameworks that go beyond compliance-based training and instead promote long-term professional growth.

The prominence of resource-related and structural barriers in the findings aligns closely with international research identifying inadequate materials, assistive technologies, and accessible infrastructure as persistent obstacles to inclusive education implementation (Bong & Chua, 2023; Keeley et al., 2020). Similar to the AISSEND observational tool, which highlighted the importance of contextual feasibility and practical applicability, the current instrument captures teachers' lived experiences of systemic constraints that limit the translation of inclusive policies into classroom practice (Keeley et al., 2020). Policy alignment and administrative support emerged as distinct yet interconnected dimensions of inclusive education readiness. This finding resonates with European policy-based research emphasizing the importance of coherent competence frameworks and leadership support in enabling inclusive professional learning (De Vroey et al., 2023). The Ethiopian context, as reflected in this study, demonstrates a gap between national inclusive education policies and their implementation at the school and teacher education levels, a challenge also noted in international comparative research.

The identification of barriers as a separate, robust factor is consistent with global studies emphasizing that teacher competence alone is insufficient without enabling environments. Studies from Colombia, India, and Malaysia similarly demonstrate that inclusive teaching competencies are shaped by systemic conditions, cultural attitudes, and institutional priorities (Bong & Chua, 2023; Chakravartya & Shindeb, 2022; Monsalve & Hernández, 2024). The strong factor loadings associated with barriers in the present study underscore the need for multi-level interventions that address curriculum design, funding, infrastructure, and policy coherence simultaneously. From a methodological perspective, the instrument's validation process reflects best practices in inclusive education measurement research. Comparable to the PERKIN scale developed by Medina-García et al. (2025), the use of expert judgment, exploratory factor analysis, and reliability testing strengthens the credibility and transferability of the findings. Although confirmatory factor analysis was not

conducted in this phase, the stable factor structure provides a strong foundation for future validation studies, including cross-regional and cross-cultural applications.

The findings also support competency-based frameworks for teacher education, which emphasize the integration of attitudes, skills, and reflective practice. Parveen (2025) and Chakravartya and Shindeb (2022) argue that inclusive education requires a paradigm shift from traditional content-driven models to competency-oriented approaches that prepare teachers for diversity. The present study's results empirically reinforce this position, demonstrating that teacher preparedness is shaped by the interaction of training quality, professional learning opportunities, and contextual support systems.

Generally, this study advances the field of inclusive education by providing a psychometrically sound, contextually grounded instrument for assessing teacher education and professional development for inclusion in Ethiopia. The findings align with and extend international research by highlighting the multidimensional nature of inclusive teaching competencies and the central role of systemic conditions in shaping teacher readiness. The validated instrument offers practical implications for teacher education institutions, policymakers, and researchers seeking to design evidence-based interventions that strengthen inclusive education practices and promote equitable learning opportunities for all students.

Conclusion

This study aimed to analyze the current state of pre-service teacher education and on-going professional development pertaining to the implementation of inclusive education in Ethiopia, while concurrently developing and validating an assessment instrument that is relevant to the specific context. The results reveal that, despite the acknowledgment of inclusive education within national policy frameworks, there exist considerable deficiencies in teacher preparation, continuous professional learning, and systemic support mechanisms. Teachers indicated moderate levels of theoretical preparedness; however, they exhibited insufficient practical competence, particularly concerning the utilization of assistive technology, curriculum adaptation, and the maintenance of inclusive practices within the classroom context. The validated multidimensional instrument offers robust empirical evidence indicating that competencies related to inclusive education are influenced not only by individual teacher knowledge and attitudes but also by the caliber of teacher education programs, opportunities for CPD, institutional leadership, and the availability of resources.

Significantly, the research underscores distinct opportunities for reform aimed at enhancing the implementation of inclusive education in Ethiopia. These opportunities encompass the reorientation of pre-service teacher education towards competency-based and practice-oriented models, the establishment of coherent and sustained frameworks for continuous professional development, and the resolution of structural and policy-level barriers that impede inclusive practices. Through providing a psychometrically validated tool and empirically grounded insights, this study contributes to evidence-based decision-making for teacher education institutions, policymakers, and professional development facilitators. Ultimately, the advancement of inclusive education in Ethiopia necessitates a systemic and coordinated approach that integrates teacher preparation, professional learning, and institutional support to ensure equitable and meaningful learning opportunities for all learners.

Limitations of the Study

Despite its contributions, this study has several limitations. First, the data were based on self-reported responses, which may be subject to social desirability and response bias. Second, the cross-sectional design limits the ability to draw causal inferences regarding the impact of training and professional development on inclusive teaching practices. Third, although the instrument demonstrated strong psychometric properties, the findings are context-specific and may not be fully generalizable beyond similar educational settings.

Finally, the study relied primarily on quantitative data; incorporating qualitative methods could provide deeper insights into teachers' lived experiences and contextual challenges related to inclusive education.

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References

- Ainscow, M., & Miles, S. (2008). Making education for all inclusive: Where next? *Prospects*, 38(1), 15-34. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1007/S11125-008-9055-0>
- Alemayehu, B. A. (2020). In-Service Primary School Teachers' Knowledge of Inclusive Pedagogy in Ethiopia. *Manisa Celal Bayar Üniversitesi Eğitim Fakültesi Dergisi*, 8(1), 17-30. <https://doi.org/https://dergipark.org.tr/tr/download/article-file/1161512>
- Banks, J., Frawley, D., & McCoy, S. (2015). Achieving inclusion? Effective resourcing of students with special educational needs. *International Journal of Inclusive Education*, 19(9), 926-943. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1080/13603116.2015.1018344>
- Beyene, W. M., Mekonnen, A. T., & Giannoumis, G. A. (2023). Inclusion, access, and accessibility of educational resources in higher education institutions: exploring the Ethiopian context. *International Journal of Inclusive Education*, 27(1), 18-34. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1080/13603116.2020.1817580>
- Bong, W. K., & Chua, K. H. (2023). Assessing Teachers' Practices in Providing Inclusive Online Education: Development and Validation of an Instrument Based on Inclusive Practices among Teachers in Malaysia. *Education Sciences*, 13(9), 1-13. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.3390/educsci13090918>
- Boyle, C., Anderson, J., & Allen, K.-A. (2020). The importance of teacher attitudes to inclusive education. In *Inclusive education: Global issues and controversies* (pp. 127-146). Brill. https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1163/9789004431171_008
- Chakravartya, D., & Shindeb, G. (2022). Inclusive Teaching Competency Model and its Applicability on Elementary School Teachers of Pune District in India. *Asian Journal of Inclusive Education*, 10(2), 91-112. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.59595/ajie.10.2.6>
- Colglazier, W. (2015). Sustainable development agenda: 2030. *Science*, 349(6252), 1048-1050. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1126/SCIENCE.AAD2333>
- Crispel, O., & Kasperski, R. (2021). The impact of teacher training in special education on the implementation of inclusion in mainstream classrooms. *International Journal of Inclusive Education*, 25(9), 1079-1090. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1080/13603116.2019.1600590>
- De Vroey, A., Lecheval, A., & Symeonidou, S. (2023). Supporting all educators to take part in teacher professional learning for inclusion. *Trends in Higher Education*, 2(2), 320-331. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.3390/higheredu2020018>
- Deckert, J., & Wilson, M. (2023). Descriptive research methods (pp. 153–165). In *University Press of Florida eBooks*. . <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.5744/florida/9780813069548.003.0011>
- Deng, M., Wang, S., Guan, W., & Wang, Y. (2017). The development and initial validation of a questionnaire of inclusive teachers' competency for meeting special educational needs in regular classrooms in China. *International Journal of Inclusive Education*, 21(4), 416-427. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1080/13603116.2016.1197326>
- EASNIE. (2012). *Teacher Education for Inclusion – Profile of Inclusive Teachers (Policy Report, Issue*.
- Florian, L. (2022). Preparing teachers for inclusive education. In *Encyclopedia of teacher education* (pp. 1374-1379). Springer. https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-16-8679-5_39
- Franck, B., & Joshi, D. K. (2017). Including students with disabilities in education for all: Lessons from Ethiopia. *International Journal of Inclusive Education*, 21(4), 347-360. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1080/13603116.2016.1197320>
- Geletu, G. M. (2024). Relevance and effectiveness of primary school teachers' professional development policy and practices in Oromia regional state, Ethiopia. *Journal of Adult and Continuing Education*, 30(1), 84-111. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1177/14779714241231241>

- Gemechui, E., & Aba-Oliiii, Z. (2024). Ethiopian college of teacher education program: A tension between selection, curriculum and professional development. *International Journal of Progressive Education*, 20(3), 1-11. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.29329/ijpe.2024.664.1>
- Haug, P. (2017). Understanding inclusive education: ideals and reality. *Scandinavian journal of disability research*, 19(3), 206-217. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1080/15017419.2016.1224778>
- Kebede, A., & Asgedom, A. (2024). Perspectives of teacher educators on the challenges of training technical and vocational education teachers in Ethiopia. *Bahir Dar Journal of Education*, 24(1), 105-123. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.4314/bdje.v24i1.8>
- Kebede, A. T., & Phasha, T. N. (2024). Developing teachers' competency for inclusive education in Ethiopia. *African Journal of Disability*, 13(1), 1383. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.4102/ajod.v13i0.1383>
- Keeley, R. G., Alvarado-Alcantar, R., & Keeley, D. W. (2020). The Development of AISSSEND: An Observation Tool to Assess Inclusive Practices. *Journal of the American Academy of Special Education Professionals*, 15(3), 122-137. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.64546/jaasep.440>
- Kudarino, A., Autaeva, A., Paylozyan, Z., & Rymkhanova, A. (2023). Readiness of Pre-Service Teachers to Implement Inclusive Education. *Wisdom*, 25(1), 145-155. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.24234/wisdom.v25i1.967>
- Laranang, J. (2025). Development and Validation of a Competency Tool for Emergency and Disaster Management for Nurses. *International Journal of Research and Innovation in Applied Science*, 9(10), 724-733. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.51584/ijrias.2024.912060>
- Medina-García, M., Ortiz-Marcos, J. M., Invernon-Gomez, A. I., & Higuera-Rodríguez, L. (2025). Educating for Inclusion: PERKIN, the Scale That Measures Future Teachers' Perceptions. *SAGE Open*, 15(3), 21582440251367584. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1177/21582440251367584>
- Miaomiao, W., DeWitt, D., Mohamad Nazry, N. N., Alias, N., Hong, L. L., & Ujang, A. (2024). Design and validity of an instrument to measure digital literacy among pre-service teachers involved in inclusive education. *International Journal of Modern Education and Computer Science*, 16(1), 84-96. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.5815/ijmecs.2024.01.07>
- Mihiretie, D. M. (2023). The pedagogy of teacher education in Ethiopia: Reconstructing understandings and practices on teaching about teaching and learning to teach. *Bahir Dar Journal of Education*, 23(2), 22-58. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.4314/bdje.v23i2.3>
- Monsalve, A. S. P., & Hernández, F. Á. P. (2024). Diseño y Validación de un Instrumento para Evaluar las Competencias Académicas del Profesorado de Primaria para la Inclusión de Estudiantes con Diagnóstico de Discapacidad. *Ciencia Latina Revista Científica Multidisciplinar*, 8(2), 1134-1151. https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.37811/cl_rcm.v8i2.10556
- Parveen, A. (2025). Breaking Barriers: Fostering Inclusivity in Teacher Education through Competency-Based Framework. *International Journal of Research and Innovation in Social Science*, 9(3), 4572-4576. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.47772/ijriss.2025.903sedu0328>
- Pasha, S., Yousaf, F., & Ijaz, M. (2021). Preparedness of prospective teachers for inclusive education: pre-service teachers' knowledge and skills. *Review of Education, Administration & Law*, 4(2), 355-363. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.47067/real.v4i2.148>
- Przibilla, B., Lauterbach, A., Boshold, F., Linderkamp, F., & Krezmien, M. (2016). Entwicklung und Validierung eines Online-Surveys zur Erhebung von Kompetenzen und Einstellungen von Lehrkräften bezüglich der Inklusion. *Empirische Sonderpädagogik*, 8(1), 36-53. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.25656/01:11853>
- Rakap, S., Cig, O., & Parlak-Rakap, A. (2017). Preparing preschool teacher candidates for inclusion: Impact of two special education courses on their perspectives. *Journal of Research in Special Educational Needs*, 17(2), 98-109. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1111/1471-3802.12116>
- Sharma, U., & Nuttal, A. (2016). The impact of training on pre-service teacher attitudes, concerns, and efficacy towards inclusion. *Asia-Pacific Journal of teacher education*, 44(2), 142-155. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1080/1359866x.2015.1081672>
- Shrestha, N. (2021). Factor analysis as a tool for survey analysis. *American journal of Applied Mathematics and statistics*, 9(1), 4-11. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.12691/ajams-9-1-2>
- Silva, D. L., Sabino, L. D., Lanuza, D. M., Adina, E. M., Villaverde, B. S., & Pena, E. G. (2014). Silva's management competency theory: a factor-item analytic approach utilizing oblique rotation direct oblmin method under Kaiser-Bartlett's test of sphericity. *Proceedings of the world congress on engineering and computer science*,
- Slee, R. (2018). Defining the scope of inclusive education. <https://doi.org/https://hdl.handle.net/20.500.12799/5977>
- Štemberger, T., & Kiswarday, V. R. (2016). Validation of the inclusive competences scale for educators (InComSEdu). *The New Educational Review*, 44(1), 243-254. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.15804/TNER.2016.44.2.20>
- Sürücü, L., Yıkılmaz, İ., & Maşlakçı, A. (2022). Exploratory factor analysis (EFA) in quantitative researches and practical considerations. *Gümüşhane Üniversitesi Sağlık Bilimleri Dergisi*, 13(2), 947-965. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.37989/gumussagbil.1183271>

Symeonidou, S. (2017). Initial teacher education for inclusion: a review of the literature. *Disability & society*, 32(3), 401-422. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1080/09687599.2017.1298992>

Tomlinson, S. (2017). *A sociology of special and inclusive education: Exploring the manufacture of inability*. Taylor & Francis. https://doi.org/https://openlibrary.org/books/OL28859957M/Sociology_of_Special_and_Inclusive_Education

Tuerah, P. R. (2025). Teacher Professional Development in Implementing Inclusive Education Practices. *NALURI EDUKASI JURNAL PENDIDIKAN*, 2(3), 117-130. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.64924/cs3h9b14>

Waitoller, F. R., & Artiles, A. J. (2013). A Decade of Professional Development Research for Inclusive Education. *Review of Educational Research*, 83(3), 319-356. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.3102/0034654313483905>

Watkins, M. W. (2018). Exploratory factor analysis: A guide to best practice. *Journal of black psychology*, 44(3), 219-246. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1177/0095798418771807>

Yusoff, M. S. B., Arifin, W. N., & Hadie, S. N. H. (2021). ABC of questionnaire development and validation for survey research. *Education in Medicine Journal*, 13(1), 97-108. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.21315/EIMJ2021.13.1.10>

Zegeye, T. (2022). The perception of readiness for implementing inclusive education among primary school subject teachers: Implications for teacher education in Ethiopia. *International Journal of Special Education*, 37(2), 82-91. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.52291/ijse.2022.37.42>

APPENDIX: DATA COLLECTION TOOL

HARAMAYA UNIVERSITY
POSTGRADUATE PROGRAM DIRECTORATE
College of Education and Behavioural Science
Department of Special Needs and Inclusive Education
Questionnaire for Primary and Secondary School Teachers

Dear respondent,

The main purpose of this questionnaire is to collect relevant data for the study titled **“Teacher Education and Continuous Professional Development for Implementing Inclusive Education in Ethiopia: Insights, Implementation Barriers and Reform Opportunities.”** The researcher assures you that the information you provide will be kept confidential and used solely for academic purposes. Thank you in advance for your cooperation and willingness to participate in this study.

General Instructions:

- You are not required to write your name.
- Please read each statement carefully.

Instruction One:

This section is about your general background information. Please write the name of your school in the space provided. For the remaining background questions, please respond by placing a “√” mark in the box that corresponds to your choice.

- 1. Name of the school:** _____
- 2. Level of the school:** primary school Secondary school
- 3. Sex:** Male Female
- 4. Age:**
 - a) 18-23 years
 - b) 24-27 years
 - c) 28-32 years
 - d) 33-37 years
 - e) 38-42 years
 - f) 43 years and above
- 5. Academic qualification:**
 - a. Diploma
 - b. Degree
 - c. Masters

d. PhD

6. Work Experience:

a. below 2 years

b. 2-4 Years

c. 5-7 Years

d. 8 years and above

Instruction Two:

Below are a series of statements regarding the training provided during your pre-service teacher education. Please read each statement carefully and indicate your opinion about the status of pre-service training by placing a “√” mark in the box that best represents your response:

- 1 = Strongly Disagree
- 2 = Disagree
- 3 = Neutral
- 4 = Agree
- 5 = Strongly Agree

Q	Question Statement	Scale				
		1	2	3	4	5
	I received adequate training on inclusive education during my pre-service training program.	1	2	3	4	5
	The pre-service training program provided me sufficient resources for learning about inclusive education.	1	2	3	4	5
	I feel confident in identifying diverse needs of students with sensory impairments.	1	2	3	4	5
	The pre-service training program enhanced my skills in identifying and addressing environmental and accessibility barriers that affect students with physical disabilities.	1	2	3	4	5
	The pre-service program emphasized the importance of collaboration with special needs educators.	1	2	3	4	5
	The pre-service training program helped me to understand how to adapt teaching strategies for students with developmental disabilities.	1	2	3	4	5
	The pre-service program included practical experiences in inclusive classrooms.	1	2	3	4	5
	The pre-service training program helped me become aware of the legal frameworks that support inclusive education in Ethiopia.	1	2	3	4	5
	The pre-service program covered strategies for managing diverse classroom behaviours.	1	2	3	4	5
	I feel prepared to address the socio-emotional needs of students with disabilities due to my pre-service training.	1	2	3	4	5
	The pre-service program provided opportunities to reflect on my own biases towards inclusion.	1	2	3	4	5
	I am familiar with assistive technologies that support students with sensory impairments due to my pre-service training.	1	2	3	4	5
	I know how to communicate effectively with parents of students with disabilities due to my pre-service training.	1	2	3	4	5
	The pre-service program emphasized the role of community in supporting inclusive education.	1	2	3	4	5
	I am confident in assessing and addressing the needs of students with physical disabilities.	1	2	3	4	5

The pre-service training program included discussions on cultural sensitivity in inclusive education.	1	2	3	4	5
I understand how to create an inclusive classroom environment for students with developmental disabilities.	1	2	3	4	5
The pre-service training program provided me opportunities for peer feedback on inclusive teaching practices.	1	2	3	4	5
The pre-service program covered strategies for promoting social inclusion among students.	1	2	3	4	5
I am aware of the challenges faced by students with disabilities in accessing education in Ethiopia as a result of the pre-service training I attended.	1	2	3	4	5
The pre-service training program emphasized the importance of teacher self-efficacy in inclusive education.	1	2	3	4	5
My pre-service training prepared me to work collaboratively with school administrators in implementing inclusive education practices.	1	2	3	4	5
The pre-service training program prepared me to advocate for inclusive education policies in my school.	1	2	3	4	5

Current State of Pre-Service Teacher Education for Inclusive Education in Ethiopia
Current State of Continuous Professional Development for Inclusive Education in Ethiopia

Instruction Three: Below are a series of questions regarding the continuous professional development for inclusive education practice in your school. Please read each question carefully and indicate your opinion about the status of CPD by placing a “√” mark in the box that best represents your response:

Question	Scale				
	Never	rarely	occasionally	Often	Always
How often do you receive CPD training on inclusive education?	Not Effective	Slightly Effective	Moderately Effective	Very Effective	Extremely Effective
How effective is the current CPD in enhancing your skills for inclusive education?	Not Relevant	Slightly Relevant	Moderately Relevant	Very Relevant	Extremely Relevant
How relevant is the CPD content to your professional development needs in teaching students with disabilities?	Not Accessible	Slightly Accessible	Moderately Accessible	Very Accessible	Extremely Accessible
How accessible are CPD resources (e.g., materials, technology) for inclusive education?	Not Supportive	Slightly Supportive	Moderately Supportive	Very Supportive	Extremely Supportive
How supportive is your school administration in facilitating CPD for inclusive education?	Not Confident	Slightly Confident	Moderately Confident	Very Confident	Extremely Confident
How confident do you feel in identifying and supporting students with sensory impairments?	Not Confident	Slightly Confident	Moderately Confident	Very Confident	Extremely Confident
How confident do you feel in identifying and supporting students with physical disabilities?	Not Confident	Slightly Confident	Moderately Confident	Very Confident	Extremely Confident
How confident do you feel in identifying and supporting students with developmental disabilities?	Not Confident	Slightly Confident	Moderately Confident	Very Confident	Extremely Confident

How often do you collaborate with colleagues to develop inclusive teaching strategies?	Never	rarely	occasionally	Often	Always
How effective are the CPD programs in promoting collaboration among teachers for inclusive education?	Not Effective	Slightly Effective	Moderately Effective	Very Effective	Extremely Effective
How well do CPD programs address the needs of students with diverse disabilities?	Not Well	Slightly Well	Moderately Well	Very Well	Extremely Well
How satisfied are you with the current CPD framework for inclusive education?	Not Satisfied	Slightly Satisfied	Moderately Satisfied	Very Satisfied	Extremely Satisfied
How often do you receive feedback on your inclusive teaching practices during CPD?	Never	rarely	occasionally	Often	Always
How useful is the feedback received during CPD in improving your teaching practices?	Not Useful	Slightly Useful	Moderately Useful	Very Useful	Extremely Useful
How supportive are CPD programs in helping you manage classroom diversity?	Not Supportive	Slightly Supportive	Moderately Supportive	Very Supportive	Extremely Supportive
How effective are CPD programs in enhancing your understanding of inclusive education policies?	Not Effective	Slightly Effective	Moderately Effective	Very Effective	Extremely Effective
How well do CPD programs align with the national inclusive education strategy?	Not Well	Slightly Well	Moderately Well	Very Well	Extremely Well
How often do CPD programs include training on assistive technology for students with disabilities?	Never	rarely	occasionally	Often	Always
How effective is the CPD in enhancing your ability to adapt curriculum for students with disabilities?	Not Effective	Slightly Effective	Moderately Effective	Very Effective	Extremely Effective
How well do CPD programs address the emotional and social needs of students with disabilities?	Not Well	Slightly Well	Moderately Well	Very Well	Extremely Well
How likely are you to recommend the current CPD framework for inclusive education to other teachers?	Not Likely	Slightly Likely	Moderately Likely	Very Likely	Extremely Likely

Instruction Four

The following statements are designed to assess your perceptions of the adequacy of training you have received for implementing inclusive education practices in Ethiopia. The focus is on teacher education and Continuous Professional Development policy frameworks and toolkits for including students with sensory impairments, physical disabilities, and developmental disabilities. Please read each statement carefully and indicate your level of agreement by placing a “√” mark in the box that best represents your response:

1 = Strongly Disagree 2 = Disagree 3 = Neutral 4 = Agree 5 = Strongly Agree

Q	Question	Scale				
	I feel I am adequately trained to teach students with sensory impairments.	1	2	3	4	5
	The current teacher education curriculum prepares me well for inclusive education.	1	2	3	4	5
	I have received sufficient CPD opportunities to enhance my skills in inclusive education.	1	2	3	4	5
	The CPD programs I attended were relevant to teaching students with physical disabilities.	1	2	3	4	5
	The CPD framework in Ethiopia addresses the needs of teachers working with students with developmental disabilities.	1	2	3	4	5
	I believe that the current teacher training programs emphasize inclusive education sufficiently.	1	2	3	4	5
	The CPD opportunities provided are tailored to address the specific needs of students with sensory impairments.	1	2	3	4	5
	I am satisfied with the level of training I received on adapting curriculum for students with disabilities.	1	2	3	4	5
	I have adequate knowledge about the legal frameworks supporting inclusive education in Ethiopia.	1	2	3	4	5
	The CPD programs have helped me develop strategies to manage diverse classroom needs.	1	2	3	4	5
	The teacher education curriculum includes sufficient content on teaching students with physical disabilities.	1	2	3	4	5
	The CPD framework ensures that teachers are updated on the latest inclusive education methodologies.	1	2	3	4	5
	The CPD programs I attended have improved my ability to create an inclusive classroom environment.	1	2	3	4	5

Barriers to equipping teachers for inclusive education practices in Ethiopia

Instruction Five: The following statements relate to possible barriers that affect equipping teachers for effective inclusive education practices in Ethiopia. Please read each statement carefully and indicate your level of agreement by placing a “√” mark in the box that best represents your response:

1 = Strongly Disagree 2 = Disagree 3 = Neutral 4 = Agree 5 = Strongly Agree

Q	Items related to barriers	Scale				
	The current teacher education curriculum doesn't covers strategies for teaching students with sensory, physical, and developmental disabilities.	1	2	3	4	5
	There is a shortage of trained educators in colleges/universities who can effectively teach inclusive education strategies.	1	2	3	4	5
	Government policies on inclusive education are not clearly communicated to teachers during training.	1	2	3	4	5
	Continuous Professional Development programs do not provide sufficient training on inclusive education for SWDs	1	2	3	4	5
	The training duration for inclusive education in pre-service programs is too short to develop necessary skills.	1	2	3	4	5
	Teaching materials (e.g., Braille, sign language guides, and adaptive tools) are lacking in teacher training institutions.	1	2	3	4	5
	School infrastructure (e.g., ramps, accessible classrooms) is not sufficiently addressed in teacher training.	1	2	3	4	5
	Assessment methods in teacher education do not adequately evaluate skills for inclusive teaching.	1	2	3	4	5
	Collaboration with special education experts during teacher training is minimal or ineffective.	1	2	3	4	5
	Awareness of disability rights and inclusion policies among teacher educators is low.	1	2	3	4	5
	Inclusive education is given low priority compared to other subjects in teacher training programs.	1	2	3	4	5
	Mentorship opportunities for new teachers on inclusive practices are insufficient.	1	2	3	4	5
	Teacher trainees receive limited hands-on experience with students with disabilities during practicum.	1	2	3	4	5
	Cultural attitudes and stigma negatively affect teacher preparedness for inclusive education.	1	2	3	4	5
	Funding for inclusive education training is inadequate in teacher education programs.	1	2	3	4	5
	Language barriers (e.g., lack of sign language training) hinder effective preparation for inclusion.	1	2	3	4	5
	Follow-up support after training (e.g., coaching, refresher courses) is lacking.	1	2	3	4	5
	Teacher educators lack practical experience in teaching students with disabilities.	1	2	3	4	5
	Classroom management strategies for diverse learners are not well-covered in training.	1	2	3	4	5
	Policy implementation gaps exist between national guidelines and actual teacher training.	1	2	3	4	5
	Limited access to inclusive education research and updated teaching methods affects training quality.	1	2	3	4	5
	Teachers feel unprepared to adapt lessons for students with developmental disabilities.	1	2	3	4	5
	CPD programs rarely include input from disability advocacy groups or specialists.	1	2	3	4	5
	Technological tools (e.g., assistive devices) are not integrated into teacher training.	1	2	3	4	5